

The Philosophy of Education in Viet Nam Nowadays

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ABSTRACT

The philosophy of education is always an essential issue of every education system. Over the past 70 years, depending on the stage of educational development, Vietnam's educational philosophy has existed and changed many times. So what is the educational philosophy in Vietnam nowadays? There are too many views on this. In this article, we present our views on this extremely important issue. The research results are based on the methodology of systematization, the methods of analysis – synthesis and comparison. We also use some conclusions of Vietnamese researchers as references. Indeed, Vietnam's educational philosophy can be divided into two periods: before 1945 and after 1945. Before 1945, Vietnam's educational philosophy was largely influenced by Confucianism, so ideal model was "quan tu" (true gentleman) people. After 1945, the country was independent, the philosophy of education was aimed at training the new socialist people. This change, on one side, meets the requirement to maintain social stability, but the other side is not paying attention to individual people and their creation. This leads to the crises of the whole education system, especially in the context of globalization and internationalization. The new context is setting new requirements for the educational philosophy of Vietnam. From a philosophical point of view, with reconsidering the human nature in general, we suppose that the new educational philosophy of Vietnam nowadays must be training freedom, creativity and bravery people, based on a human. In this article, we will raise different views of many scholars about it and present our points of views on this extremely important issue. In this article, we will denote different conceptions of many scholars about it and take our view on this extremely important issue. Hereafter indicating the educational achievements of Vietnam in the past, we introduce the system of perceptions about the human in Vietnamese society today and regarding this as the basis for building the philosophy of education and showing the basic ideas of the educational philosophy, which exists in Vietnam nowadays. Finally, we state our views on this issue. It is a combination of ideas that are difficult to say in a sentence.

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INTRODUCTION

The education of every nation is built on five pillars, such as the educational philosophy or the educational goal; Content, curriculum, teaching methods, assessment organization, or what to learn and how to learn; Teaching staff or who teach ?; Facilities, equipment, financially...And finally, the educational management system, or how to learn? Therefore the philosophy of education is always the vital issue of every education. In this report, we will present the current philosophy of education in Vietnam. The article has 4 sections. Part 1 discusses the overview of the history of Vietnamese educational attitudes, Part 2 presents the way of looking at the human in Vietnamese society today, Part 3 discusses the basic ideas to build the educational philosophy

for Vietnam in the future, part 4 is the conclusions and recommendations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The first of all, we use the referral systems and supplementary tools such as computers to calculate the index, to draw the chart, questionnaires to ask students, educators and administrators about their views on the educational philosophy of Vietnam nowadays, as the principal materials. For research, we use the method of analysis and quantitative data from the questionnaires, writing synthesis, survey and evaluation results, discussion by the group and report partial results in the seminar and comparing the results of research theory with practice to conclude.

RESULTS

1 / Overview of the history of Vietnamese educational attitudes

1.1. The Democratic Republic of Vietnam, today is the Socialist Republic of Vietnam was born in 1945. Modern Vietnamese education, as it began. Over the past 70 years, Vietnam's education has attained great achievements. From an unnamed country on the world map, 90% of the illiterate population, almost without any significant educational achievement, Vietnam became an independent country, out of poverty. More clearly, these are the following achievements (Hoang Tuy. 2013; Ministry of Education and

Training. 2014): 1/ Development of education for all people; Increasing the scale of the school system. Today, in Viet Nam, on average, one in four people is in school; 2/ Implementing social equality and gender equality in education, providing policies for disadvantaged learners; 3/ The quality of training has been developing step by step; The teachers, increasing management staff and quality development, and education management policies are increasingly renewed; 4/ Better education facilities, Vietnam spends about 5% of GDP, 20% of the total state budget for education (Nguyen Thi Nga. 2017, see the figures 1, 2); 5/ International integration in education is better and broader.

Figure 1: Percentage of expenditure on education and formation compared to the total public expenditure of Vietnam and compare it with some countries (%)

Source: World Bank

Figure 2: Percentage of expenditures for education and training compared to Vietnam's GDP and compare it with some countries (%)

Source: World Bank

But besides that, the weakness of education is also very high (Ministry of Education and Training. 2014): 1/ The education quality on a large scale, especially at the university level is low, methods of education are backwards, and slow innovation; 2/ The conditions to ensure the development of education show still many inadequacies; 3/ There are many difficulties in accessing education, especially in higher education for children of poor families, low-income families and children of ethnic minorities; 4/. Some negative phenomena in education are slowly resolved (for example, extra teaching and extra-curricular activities, selling diplomas, achievement obsession,...); An education system to get a degree.; Studying for the exam. Even, these weaknesses caused the four major diseases of the Vietnamese education system are: a disease of achievement obsession, a disease of the level (egalitarianism), malnutrition and cheating disease (Tran Ngoc Them. 2016), which partly due to disunited educational philosophy.

There are too many views on this issue. Some people think that Vietnam does not have any educational philosophy (Nguyen Quoc Vuong, 2017). Some people say that "Vietnam has an educational philosophy. But only that, we do not have the quotes to be canonical (Vietnam Education Newspaper. 2016)". Someone said: "If we assemble representatives of educational administrators, teachers, students, somebody in the same examination room and ask them to describe the Vietnamese educational philosophy, then we will obtain many things which are very different. Someone can write something. And some will probably return the blank paper. ". It's too funny. Until recently, there are still research papers like "What is the philosophy of education in Vietnam?", "The journey to find the modern education philosophy in Vietnam". If it was there and it was clear enough, consistent, persuasive, what would it be? It had to be printed in some book or document. So it may be that it has not yet been, or has been, but not sufficiently clear, consistent, persuasive to be a fundamental system of education. Where is this philosophy of education? It is not in the goodness that we declare, but in the practice of everyday education. This practice is due to the demands of society.

1.2. Analyzing more carefully, some people think that: Looking back on the history of Vietnamese education, in the Confucian education system, the philosophy of education is encapsulated in an output product, namely: it trained the honest to do Mandarin. It is through this philosophy that the Confucian education system has existed for over two thousand years. Only when the model of the honest, that is the output of this system, is no longer suitable for the new era, this system of education has just collapsed. But since Viet Nam gained independence in 1945, Vietnam's educational philosophy has never been so explicit and concise in education reforms, except for a previous official statement: training new socialist people. But what is the new socialist human being? This is the ideal man, no real model.

The educational philosophy, in the most general sense, is to be brief, directional, and is the foundation of thinking, following the culture or stage of history. In this sense, several people see that: The Vietnamese philosophy carries on the systematic defects; those disabilities cannot be repaired in sundry, patchy, but "thinking back" starting from a systematic approach; The essence of this thinking flow is: Returning the autonomy of education, and the State only performs the function of macro-management, science and education system need to be restructured on an autonomous basis. This is necessary objectivity, on the path of reform from a command economy to a market economy (Vu Cao Dam. 2007; Vu Cao Dam. 2014).

1.3. It's hard to imagine an education that lacks an educational philosophy. And the phrase that the education of Vietnam has no educational philosophy, is also difficult to accept. But if Vietnamese education has an educational philosophy, how does that philosophy reveal? And what's included? Nowadays, there are still so many diverse ideas and debates. The viewpoints that Vietnam has an educational philosophy often illustrated by the following examples: "First is good manners, Second is knowledge", "Learning with practice", "You do not make a fool of yourself," "To go through, they must be bridged. For the children study well, must love the teacher". "For the sake of ten years, the tree must be planted. "An ignorant nation is a weak nation." In these sentences, some may be considered as educational philosophies, for example: "First is good manners, Second is knowledge", "Learning with practice". Some of the other sentences are not educational philosophies, but they are about attitudes toward the job of teaching, teachers, and the importance of education and teachers.

Among sentences that can be considered as educational philosophies, there are ones that have existed for hundreds of years and have not yet been verified, affirmed they are still conformity with or not to the new era of education? "First is good manners, second is knowledge", this is the idea of Confucian education, emphasizing the priority and importance of teaching ethics as compared to the teaching of knowledge and skills. Does this idea still fit the needs for lifelong learning? Does it fit the learning objectives of the "Learning to Know, Learn to Do, Learn to Live Together, Study for Self-Esteem" by UNESCO that we have also chosen?

1.4. Some people think: Vietnamese traditional society is the agricultural society of wet rice cultivation, and it is very nature of negative, with the basic characteristic is just desire to live quietly, and stably. To be stable, society needs good and obedient men. Therefore, the traditional educational philosophy of Vietnam can be summed up in four words that all Vietnamese people, Vietnamese schools often use, "good children, excellent student." "Good children" are obedient ones (the child against the parent is a debauched child), "good student", should learn something by heart (question the teacher's mouth is usually "learned lessons?"). In other words,

it is a stable educational philosophy (Tran Ngoc Them. 2016). Once an education has been oriented, it is difficult to exist without voluntarism. Therefore, education cannot teach students the things life needs only equips them with the will needs. Equally speaking, this educational philosophy has served very well to create stability in traditional Vietnamese society.

But today is different. Now is the era of industrialization, modernization and integration; society is not inward-looking but needs to be extroverted; old stability achieved by standing still, looking back, and today a stable society must be developed society, looking to the future. Because of the unsuitable educational philosophy of "good children, good pupil" for the era and philosophy of education towards stability, which has created tragedy and caused obstacles in education in Vietnam today. First of all, it creates a society of desires to repute rather than learning. Desire to learn is covetousness that urges us to have the knowledge and use the things learned in life. While the Vietnamese students in school in the past only needed to pass the exam to have dignitary (in a stable society as the head is enough); but today if a student goes to school just to pass exams to obtain a degree and after leaving school, they forget all and work poorly, "desire to learn" in such a way, how can the country develop? The educational philosophy is stable then it is associated with a society where everything is subsidized; The subsidy of Vietnam has been long gone, but because it is rooted in culture, the subsidy phenomenon still exists: In the family, parents subsidize their children; at school, the teachers subsidize students; At the national level, the ministry subsidize for schools and the state subsidize the people. Do social subsidizations lead to a mechanism of "ask - give". How can the country develop?

The educational philosophy towards stable consenting a view of the small farmers, only to see the goal very close. It spawns a lot of bad consequences. The goal of "good children, good pupil good" and vision of small farmers make the Vietnamese that when doing anything they also deal only, Include all questions about the types of sample exercises to teach how to solve. Therefore, in many international competitions, Vietnamese students often take good examinations. But life is not the test, and all solutions are not available in the sample exercises. Life requires creativity. The educational philosophy of "good children, good pupils" leads to a very strange conception of limiting the size of textbooks. The curriculum of Vietnamese general education is limited to 70-80 pages and the textbook for university-level is in the range of 200-300 pages. It is because of the influence of the educational philosophy of "good children, good pupils" that everywhere, we have restored the slogan "First is good manners, Second is knowledge".

1.5. Another approach can view the philosophy of education in Vietnam, first of all, is the philosophy of building a country with rich people, strong country, democracy, justice, and literature. It is the building of the whole Vietnamese people,

with good moral, good knowledge, good health, good sense of beauty, national spirit, patriotism and an international responsibility ". It is aimed at goals as UNESCO has set out (that is learning to know, learn to do, learn to self assert, learn to make a living). Saying that, since ancient times, our education has been directed to human beings - humanity, open mind but not root, that is the national self-respect, patriotic but not narrow-minded which is tied to the international consciousness regarding consciousness of "global citizen" nowadays.

2 / The conception of a human in Vietnamese society today

2.1. Many studies of philosophy, society, and humanity usually start with human evaluation and analysis. In particular, to find the philosophy of education for a society, it is necessary to recognize the conception of human (Nguyen Dinh Cong. 2017). Evolutionary theory holds that mankind is from apes. Karl Marx and many philosophers believe it, but others do not believe. Some religions claim that man was created by God. Buddhism teaches that people go through many lifetimes. According to Russian scientist Mundasep (Tran Trung Phuong. 2012), humanity is now the 5th generation on The Earth, in which each generation lasts several tens of millions of years. Four previous generations have appeared and been destroyed. But the human was not destroyed, their race remained, passed from this generation to the other generation. However, for survival and development, the question of origin is not as important as the existence of human beings, such as the purpose of life, the motive of life, and human rights.

2.2. There are many studies about human nature, from ancient times until now. In ancient Greece, Socrates said that "man does not want brutal cruelty," Plato notes, "Man is governed by greed." In ancient China, Confucianists said that "the human's primordial nature is good", and on the contrary, the legalist confirmed the sect advocates of law advocate see that "The origin of man is evil." Buddhism accepts that every person has "Buddha nature". Besides, the eastern Philosophy states that "human life is the same universe". Recently, Edgar Morin, the French philosopher and anthropologist, wrote the book "Human characteristics", which essentially represents the creation of human complexes.

2.3. Understanding the concept of "Human is small Universe" leads us to realize that the universe and man are made up of two parts, Material and Spirit. These two parts are closely intertwined in unity. With humans, the material which makes up the body is the object of scientific research. Spirituality is the object of study of religion and some mystical subjects. Astronomer Trinh Xuan Thuan said: "To develop, science does not need spirituality, as well as spirituality, does not need science. But with humans, to develop comprehensively need to know both "(Trinh Xuan Thuan. 2016). Thus, discussing human nature that ignores the spiritual part is not comprehensive. The spiritual part consists of information and energy.

2.4. Many people think that human nature is formed from two sources: "The at Anteriority" (The First) and "The after Anteriority" (The Later). The First is the human part that receives before birth, it is inherited from parents, breeders, and spiritual sources through generations. The Later is the receiving part and it's formed in life, it consists of several things, including relationships. Particularly about the relationship, there are four bonds. That is 1-relationship between man and nature; 2- relations between people and people; Self-relationships within each human being; 4. The relationship between human beings and the spiritual world (Nguyen Dinh Cong. 2017). For human beings, material forms the body. There are two types of body activities: conscious and unconscious. Conscious activity is commanded by the brain, which determines the wisdom, the foolishness, and the failure of man. Active unconsciousness which is uncontrolled by the brain is the activity of organs and biological systems, it determines health and life. Between these two types of activities, the connection bridge is the respiratory tract. The breath is active in both unconscious and conscious. It is possible to use conscious breathing exercises to regulate some unconscious activities thereby, improving health and curing diseases. The spiritual part of man how it is composed and how mysterious, even with modern science. But there are also many people feeling it, it is including energy and information. All of the human information, temporarily called the Mind, consists of two parts. Consciousness and Subconscious. Consciousness belongs to the activity of the brain with the reception of the information of the five senses. The Spiritual consciousness belongs to the spirit, part of it comes from the first heaven, other parts are received through the field of the halo. The epistemology of Buddhism says that the subconscious is stored in the so-called hidden part of consciousness. There is the exchange of information between the activity of the brain and the subconscious in that the transition from the brain into the subconscious is initiative, the subconscious transition into the brain is automatic (this transformation creates a premonition). Many people study consciousness suppose that it's like icebergs that the consciousness is the floating part of the water, it consists of very small parts, the subconscious mind is submerged in water, it consists of a large portion of the ice sheet. Consciousness, in addition to the usual functions that we have known it also the bridges connections between body and spirit, just as breathing is the bridge between conscious and unconscious activity. Epistemology for that the main function of the brain is the operating organ, and most important human decisions are made from consciousness (Nguyen Dinh Cong. 2017).

2.5. Karl Mark states that "human nature is the sum of social relationships" (The Complete Book, vol. 3, p.11). In my opinion, this concept is right but not sufficient because it only reflects a small part of human The above Karl Mark's conclusions are based on social research and are especially influenced by the theory of evolution. If you understand

social relations in a narrow scope, you can see that people who support this theory, often ignore many essential qualities of human nature. Several views are expanding our social relationships into relationships with nature and relationships with ourselves. On other hands, some people believe that social relations include human biological issues. But even if they deliberately expand the concept of social relations to enrich one's human notion as the sum of social relationships, it does not help us escape from the narrow view.

In organisms (including humans), anything that belongs to them is the result of the combination of two things: the variety and the environment in which the variety is decisive and the environment is very important. But the theory of evolution too much emphasis on the role of the environment, which is slightly considered in terms of species. We have been affected by this concept and we have a short-sighted view of man, it was argued that social relations were the primary environment, determining the nature of human beings.

2.6. What is human nature? Many views on this matter (Journal of Philosophy. 2014), in that, Vietnam was greatly influenced by the concept of people from Buddhism and Chinese thinkers. Buddhism considers man as the union between identity and identity (material and spiritual). The eternal life is Nirvana, where the human soul is liberated to become immortal. The Confucius conceived that: Human nature is governed by "the destiny giving by The God", virtue of "human" is the highest value of human beings, especially for the honest man. The Mencius has converged human nature into the innate capacity, due to the influence of customs, bad habits should be removed from the good. Therefore, through the thought and training to keep his moral. Yuan Zi (He was a Confucianist, Chinese thinker at the end of the Warring States Period) has said that the nature of human beings at birth is evil, but can be converted, must fight evil, human beings are good. Tung Chung-Shu (He was the idealist philosopher of the Western Han Dynasty, a typical representative of Confucianism) was the successor of Confucianism following the extreme idealistic trend. He conceives that Heaven and Man can understand each other (Heaven and Human are touched). Human life is determined by "the heavenly" ("the destiny giving by The God"). Lao Tzu (He was the main character in Chinese philosophy) saw the human being born from the "Moral Principle". Therefore, human beings need to live "doctrine of spontaneity" following nature principle, not anti-natural. It can be said that Eastern philosophy expresses the diversity and abundance of human beings but in the direction of human beings in political and moral relations. In general, the man in the Eastern philosophy expresses the idealism that blends innocent naivety about nature and society.

Apart from influences from the East, Vietnamese culture is heavily influenced by the Western philosophy of human notions. Christianity: Christianity conceives that human beings are corpses and souls. The body is lost, but the soul is eternal. Therefore, it is necessary to take care of the soul

regularly to reach eternal Paradise. Ancient Greeks: Man is a small universe in the vast universe. The middle Ages: Humans are the product of God. The earthly life is temporary, happiness is in the afterlife. Renaissance philosophy: Man is an intellectual entity. German Classical Philosophy: G.G.Hegel argues that man is the embodiment of "absolute thought", while L. Feuerbach has said that humans are the result of the development of nature. Man and nature are unified, inseparable.

2.7. So, man is a unified entity between the biological and social aspects: The biological aspect, which includes the body and the body needs and biological laws dominating the life of the human body. Social aspects include "the sum of social relationships", the social activities, the spiritual life of people. Man is the subject and the product of history: There is no natural world, no social history then no human beings. Therefore, man is the product of history, of the long evolution of the living world. But the most important is that man is always the subject of history - society. As a social entity, humanly operates in practice, human impacts on nature, change the natural world, it also promotes the movement and development of social history. In the process of transforming the natural world, people also make the history of themselves. Man is the product of history and the creator of the history of man himself. Human nature is not a closed system, but an open system, corresponding to the condition of a human's existence.

From that it can be said: The most basic personality of man is personal, people always attach importance to, "ego". In human nature there is both good and evil seed, apart from the at anteriority (The First), the other is sown from the after anteriority (The Laster). Good or evil, in which good or evil is suppressed, good or evil is developed that is because they get the conditions from the environment. Therefore, to develop human nature positively, it is necessary to make the situation more and more human. Man receives the situation positively and reacts to the situation in different many respects. It is the dialectic of the relationship between the person and the situation, at any stage of human social history.

3 / Basic ideas to build Vietnam's educational philosophy in the future

3.1. In short, the educational philosophy is a statement of thought, but concise, usually in one sentence, everyone understands and can do. As a result, the philosophy of education has become the guideline for all teaching and learning activities, and more broadly, all activities related to human development, following the culture or stage of history. Education philosophy is not far away, but at the output of the education system, that is, in the people that the education system produces. In other words, the educational philosophy will be found in answering the most important question: What are people which education system is directed towards training?

Given such importance, the educational philosophy is not just ideological orientation, but also the soul, countenance of the whole system of education. Based on the educational philosophy that the entire educational system, as well as the activities, are designed, operation and adjustment. Being a soul, countenance, educational philosophy will automatically appear to all concerned. Then we will see the philosophy of education, feel the philosophy of education, be understanding the philosophy of education at a very subtle level, from student to teacher, to the parents in the house, not only the experts understand. Instead of training human of tools, education must shift the direction for training a free human. Then the creative human and human being will naturally appear.

In other words, when there is an educational philosophy, it will appear as natural as it is in everyday life and exist in all educational activities and is understood in the same way. If not, then some statements or studies on education, no matter how thorough elaboration, it is not the philosophy of education, but the philosophical theory of education, or the study of special of education.

To do so, the philosophy of education must be explicitly and convincingly addressed by the state administration itself, such as the Ministry of Education and Training. Otherwise, it will not have the righteousness to become the overall operating system for the whole system.

3.2. Vietnam education philosophy must conceive: Vietnam education is humane education. Human philosophy lays something down as a policy that man has an important place in this world; take the human as the root, take the life of man in this life as the basis; considering human beings as a means of life, not as a means or instrument for any individual, partisan, or other organization. Human philosophy accepts the difference between individuals, but does not accept the use of that distinction for human evaluation, and does not accept discrimination or rich or poor, local or religious discrimination, , race, etc. With the philosophy of humanity, people are equally valued and have the right to equal educational opportunities. Education in Vietnam is a national education. Education respects the traditional values of the nation in all activities related to family, occupation, and nation. Education must preserve and promote the essence or best traditions of the national culture. The cultural character of the culture must be known, preserved and promoted by generations, so as not to be lost or dissolved in other cultures. Vietnamese education is a liberal education. Nationalism is not necessarily conservative, not necessarily closed. In contrast, education must expand, to receive advanced scientific and technical knowledge in the world, receiving the spirit of democracy, development, the value of human culture to contribute to the modernization of the nation and society, make progressive society accessible to world civilization. Learning is to explore and be creative. Education is to provide learners with exploration and creativity; Educate people to

love, share, unite, join hands to build the society, living in harmony with nature.

3.3. Vietnam has experienced many wars in the past, where compliance is at the forefront, it is a favourable environment for human as a tool (tool human) promotes effectively. This circumstance makes training the tool human seem reasonable and suit the needs, without being questioned, in addition to the traditional Confucian culture of backwardness and orderliness, one-way adherence, this has contributed to the weakness of Vietnamese education become serious. We are always taught the understanding, know and behave in a predefined pattern. But now, before the challenge to innovate, especially when the 4.0 industrial revolution is staging impetuously, the training human as a tool must be questioned and removed. If without changing training from now on, the failure of the tool people will sure, will be firm in hand. Why? Because with the speed of technology development in now, compete with humans act as a tool against machines, humans have no way of winning machines. Occupations that use too much human muscle will not survive. The automation chain that runs on rice and food at that time also disappears. In the factory, the robot arm will take over most of the work. Cars can drive themselves. Computer self-study. The tool people are not capable of creativity, they only know the stereotype of what has been taught. What will they do in that situation? So, absolutely, instead of training tool people, education must turn to train for a free human. Then, creative people, the human being will naturally appear. As long as that is not achieved, Vietnam's educational reform is still in the deadlock.

3.4. The core solution for education in Vietnam, of course, is to change the philosophy of education from the direction of stability to development, from "good children, good pupil" to brave children, creativity. Society wants to develop, culture must be positive about. That means that society must be truly democratic and operate under the rule of law, humans have to give up the village community instead, it is the person having stuff and a sense of community. We must evaluate and honesty is more than a cute, clever. To have to take a sense of responsibility instead of relying on; To have to take the spirit of cooperation for the common rather than the appearances, face, join the faction, group; Have to have scientific and creative in place of coping, arbitrarily. These values must become the target that Vietnam's education reform needs to be awarded. From the philosophy of education and goals, we will consider issues such as the structure of education levels, programs, textbooks as appropriate and we will change fundamentally the method of teaching, evaluation; thinking, the work's way of the teachers and the educational management system of each school (Tran Ngoc Tham. 2016).

3.5. Education model must be changed. The current educational model consists of three components: family-school-society. And it has existed for over 50 years. They look at this model as a triangle with each element as a vertex. That's not true. This is the typical product of educational

philosophy of direction to the subsidized society when everyone is participating in education, meanwhile, the object of education itself is completely forgotten, students are nothing in the educational model. The school is part of society; Society is part of the school and so is the relationship of the family to the school.

So, have to change and find a new model: The model may consist of five components, the most important of which, the central element is the object of education itself. The child must be gradually involved in education, ultimately self-determination, it must be the person most responsible for his / her learning. The Family, The School, The Society play the role of orientation, counselling, service, support. Finally, The State creates all institutional and legal frameworks ... for the training of human beings. With such an educational philosophy and educational model, everything will change, for example as over: The School is part of society and The Society is part of the school.

3.6. If everyone has the firm stuff the society will be diversified. Because of their bravery and stuff, everyone thinks differently. Learn one subject, but each will learn differently. Each person is a unique world no one like, not as robots are produced from the same factory. Diversification of society, diversity of thought, that is the real society of man. Diversity, but altogether for the best purpose for society, not as Vietnam did in the past, training is a common pattern and when going to society, everyone is strong, but cannot cooperate. This is a difficult process. But overcome this difficulty, the education of Vietnam can get human beings, the educational system of "good children, good pupil" is replaced the educational system of "bravery child, creative pupil", is to create real human beings, is to develop learner capacity and is to teach people, is oriented towards quality and output rather than degrees of diploma (Tran Ngoc Them. 2016).

3.7. There are experts said that Vietnam's education is discordant, not backward but discordance out of the world, on the other way, alone, and so there is no hope of being integrated into the world to be able to follow the world. Thus, it must be changed from the root (Sail Club. 2017). We want to train free man, known thinking and independent thinkers, from these are creative people for a free and creative society or educate people who only implement, obedient, submissives, are easily commanded? There is a person or some people that they think everything for everyone and people just memorize it and follow it, follow them. It is the source of inadequacies of all educational issues. Therefore, to overcome this situation, even, in a way, this is a matter of survival for the development of nation and country (Hoang Tuy. 2012; Sail Club. 2017). Have to modernize the education system. But how modern education? We believe that a modern educational system is first and foremost in the modernity of the educational philosophy that it pursues. And the philosophy of modern education is to build an education in which is not meant to be Sophisticated machines charged

with a huge memory knowledge as we are trying to make today but to create free people, know and dare to think independently self-gaining knowledge, find out the truth, right by them-self, from that, they mastered their lives, their country and humanity. In the general situation, have to transfer the conception of "human beings" (original inhabitants) to the view of "human beings", It means that man belongs to all mankind, and not just to a nation (Nguyen Ngoc. 2009).

3.8. An educational philosophy that aims to create a free person is also a requirement for an educational method that is different from the one we are currently doing in schools. This educational method first requires maximum respect of the learner, students are not considered as insensitive jars, passive to allow us to pour knowledge into, they are creators, they have infinite creative potential, it should be elicited so that the potential is open and active, even when they are opened, it can be large, they are more creative than we expected, they surpass their teachers, over the books (Nguyen Ngoc. 2009). This is a liberal education.

3.9. History of Western countries shows only after the secularization of the school, separation of schools from the Catholic Church, modern science and technology have strong conditions to develop, at the same time, the Church does not thereby lose its spiritual position in society. To us, the ultimate goal of the nation is to be a rich people, a strong country, a democratic society, a fair, It also needed a similar solution for education that could open the way to make prosper of the country. has long been in our lives, it was demanding that the school must escape the ideological subsidy and rigid catechetical constraints, it is holding back, instead, it is necessary to enlighten the mind, should emphasize the humanities: personality training, intellectual qualities, sensory capacity, sense of community, as in every advanced school in the world. That is to teach people in the highest noble sense (Hoang Tuy. 2013).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. One of the core solutions for the development of education in Vietnam is changing the philosophy of education from the direction of stability to development and from "good children" to children having bravery and students daring to create. It is Necessary to have educational philosophy with the goal above, before considering other issues of education. Particularly, in the first steps, to develop university education to be the leader. Therefore, the biggest challenge of Vietnamese education nowadays is to modernize the university education, to promote scientific research to improve the quality of training (Nguyen Huynh Phan. 2015), bring the higher education integrate truly into the path of development of the world. Have to throw away the backward, stagnant pulling us, to move strongly following the model of higher education in the United States which is an advanced model that is being applied universally in the world. We can say that the success or failure of education reform in Vietnam

today, a decisive part depends on the progress of this university education modernization.

2. Vietnam can refer to the foundations that the American Education philosophy has relied upon, that are the five core theories including Essentialism, Perennialism, Progressivism, Social Reconstructionism and Existentialism (Luong Hoai Nam. 2014).

The Essentialism promotes the teaching of the substantive content of the classic knowledge and moral, encourage the school to return to the basics, based on a strong core education program and high standards of classics.

The Perennialism focuses on universal truths that are tested over time, encouraging students to read "The Great Books" to develop the perception of philosophical perspectives laying the groundwork for human knowledge.

The Progressivism requires that the content of the lectures at school be relevant to the students so that they wish to learn. The curriculum of the school follows this educational philosophy is built around the experience, interests, individual needs of students and create interest, passion for learning.

The Social Reconstructionism as the philosophy of education requires is the direct and timely attention to the evils, too bad habits in society, promote learning with action, based on the belief that education can and should improve and solve social problems.

The Existentialism comes from the point of view about freedom of consciousness of each person and the need for each person to create their future. In a school, students are encouraged to understand and promote their uniqueness and take responsibility for his actions.

3. Education reform in Vietnam needs to be resolute, promptly, but not in a hurry, it is necessary to draw up a roadmap and a can concrete implementation plan. In the short term, to implement reforms at urgent stages, have to organize research on specific issues such as curriculum and textbooks for the general education level, teaching methods at all levels, testing innovation, etc. from a new thinking point of view. We know that in the situation of our country there are many difficulties, but this is also the opportunity to educate can change one's look, from a kind of education of dogmatic strongly, backward and out of place with the times and the world, moving on to the education enlightened, healthy, honest, modern, accordance with the general trend of humanity and response the supreme benefits of the country, liberal education to create the Vietnamese people having humanity, free, creation and integration with the world (Hoang Tuy. 2013; Hoang Tuy. 2013 (book)).

The wishes and suggestions we present above will surely come, it is possible to believe so through the citation system in our article, it's mostly taken from the Internet, meaning to say, the discussions on the search and development of the educational philosophy of Vietnam moved inspires freely.

The President Ho Chi Minh was the great leader of the Vietnamese people, has left the Vietnamese people and

humanity a valuable truth, when He has asserted "There is nothing more precious than independence, freedom." So, In Vietnam was independent, we will achieve all the next things, including, we will create an educational philosophy for Vietnam to develop together with humanity.

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